

Non-target effects of *Bacillus thuringiensis* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* on egg parasitoids of *Spodoptera frugiperda*

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HIGHLIGHT

- Reduction in adult emergence from post-parasitism *Bt* use is below the IOBC 30% limit.
- Both *Bt* and *M. anisopliae* are compatible with *T. chilonis* at recommended doses.
- Applying *Bt* immediately after the release of *T. chilonis* is not recommended.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

The graphical abstract is created via biorender (BioRender.com)

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ABSTRACT

Biological control is regarded as the most important green measures to control agricultural pests. It is valuable to understand the compatibility between microbial pesticides and natural enemies. This study aimed to assess the non-target effects on *Trichogramma chilonis*, a predominant egg parasitoid of the major maize pest *Spodoptera frugiperda* (fall armyworm, FAW) by two commonly used maize field biopesticides: *Bacillus thuringiensis* G033A (*Bt*) and *Metarhizium anisopliae* CQMa421. In laboratory and semi-field experiments guided by IOBC protocols, neither biopesticide interfered with the parasitism efficiency or developmental duration of *T. chilonis* when applied before parasitism. Similarly, post-parasitism application didn't affect the parasitoid's host-seeking behavior. However, *Bt* application on parasitized eggs resulted in a 23.5 % reduction in adult parasitoid emergence rate, though the magnitude of this effect remained below the IOBC safety threshold (<30 %). There was no harm found on the parasitoids by *M. anisopliae* under all tested conditions. Thus, both biopesticides are largely compatible with *T. chilonis* for FAW control. The study disclosed that it is necessary to consider the optimal timing for the use of microbial pesticides and the release of natural enemies to enhance their synergistic pest control efficacy in field conditions. *Bt* application should be avoided immediately after parasitoids release.

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1. Introduction

Biological control agents (BCAs) have gained significant attention as sustainable solutions for plant health issues, with increasing global adoption. Among BCAs, macrobial agents (parasitoids and predators), also referred to as invertebrate biological control agents (IBCAs), are insects, mites, or nematodes capable of controlling agricultural pests (Deiss, 2023). In integrated pest management (IPM) programs (Kogan, 1998), macrobial agents are often used in conjunction with biopesticides. The commercialization of these products has expanded considerably, with many companies mass-producing various parasitoids and predatory insects (Luck and Forster, 2003).

Nearly 40 % of biological pest control cases have used parasitoids as IBCAs. Meanwhile, entomopathogenic fungi (EPFs) applications account for 13.6 % of cases, and predatory beetles, 9.3 % (Stiling and Cornelissen, 2005). Hymenopteran parasitoids, which include *Trichogramma* species, have proven highly effective in suppressing populations of many crop pests (Parra et al., 1987; Willow et al., 2019). Together, these findings underscore the critical role of macrobial agents as environmentally friendly alternatives to chemical pesticides. This role is particularly paramount in managing invasive pests like the Fall Armyworm (FAW, *Spodoptera frugiperda*), which poses a significant threat to global food security and necessitates the integration of multiple biological control strategies.

China is one of the countries with the most extensive use of augmentative releases of *Trichogramma* species for pest control (Xiang and Zhang, 2011). *Trichogramma chilonis* (Ishii) (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae) is one of the most important parasitic natural enemy insect species (Navik et al., 2021), for Lepidopteran pests. *Trichogramma* species have been investigated for biological control applications in many parts of the world (Lingathurai et al., 2015; Pinto and Stouthamer, 1994). The efficacy of *T. chilonis* against the FAW has been demonstrated, and it is now widely adopted in pest management programs (Li et al., 2019b).

However, the rapid and potent suppression offered by chemical pesticides often leads to an over-reliance on them, overshadowing their long-term drawbacks (Duraimurugan and Lakshminarayana, 2018), leading to insecticide resistance and pest resurgence (Roy et al., 2017). Most broad-spectrum insecticides, such as spinosad, chlorfenapyr, chlorpyrifos, triazophos, imidacloprid (Chen et al., 2013), as well as azadirachtin and deltamethrin (Thubru et al., 2018), cannot be used in conjunction with releases of parasitoids, including species of *Trichogramma*, due to their high acute toxicity or side effects to Hymenoptera. To address this challenge, microbial control agents (MCAs), particularly entomopathogenic fungi (EPFs) such as *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metchnikoff) Sorokin (Erlar and Ates, 2015) and bacteria like *Bacillus thuringiensis* Berliner (*Bt*) (Lacey, 2017), have been considered as more compatible alternatives in crops where parasitoids are released.

Within the IPM framework, the coordinated use of BCAs and biopesticides is crucial for sustainable pest management, and their compatibility highly depends on the selection of agents, application dosage, and timing. IPM seeks to maximize natural controls (e.g., predatory insects and parasitic wasps), using only compatible pesticides as auxiliary tools when necessary. This requires careful coordination of pesticide choice, dosage, and application timing with the activity patterns of natural enemies (Nasreen et al., 2003; Schuld and Schmuck, 2000; Youn et al., 2003). Integrating compatible pesticides with key biological control agents is particularly important for the sustainable management of crop pests. For example, studies have demonstrated the combined application of biopesticides and *T. chilonis* to control the cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera*) (Balakrishnan et al., 2004). A regimen of two *T. chilonis* releases plus two *Bt* sprays proved most effective in reducing larval numbers and fruit damage, outperforming a schedule combining parasitoid releases with *H. armigera* nucleopolyhedrosis virus applications. Similarly, Ramu et al. (2022) demonstrated that in maize, a combination of seed treatments, the biocontrol agent

T. chilonis, and the microbial pesticide *M. anisopliae* effectively mitigated FAW damage and improved yields.

To optimize pest management strategies, it is essential to identify pesticides that effectively control pests while posing minimal risks to natural enemies. Previous research has proposed sequential evaluations from laboratory to field studies to identify pesticides with the least impact on biological control agents (Croft et al., 1990).

The practical management of FAW presents a particular challenge due to generational overlap and the continuous occurrence of egg masses and larvae in the field demand that control strategies possess rapid, sustained, and compatible multi-method capabilities. In China, *Bt* and *M. anisopliae* are commonly registered microbial pesticides for FAW control, while *T. chilonis* is the most widely used egg-parasitizing natural enemy. Theoretically, combining highly effective microbial insecticides with actively foraging parasitoids holds the potential to achieve integrated control of FAW eggs and larvae, leading to synergistic effects.

However, the realization of this potential critically depends on a precise understanding of their compatibility, particularly regarding the timing of applications specifically, whether applying microbial pesticides before, after, or concurrently with parasitoid release would impair the efficacy of the parasitoids or, conversely, yield positive impacts due to sublethal effects on the host pests. Although some studies have examined the individual toxicity of *Bt* and *M. anisopliae* to *Trichogramma* wasps, there is a clear lack of evidence-based operational guidelines on how to sequentially apply these two mainstream microbial pesticides alongside *T. chilonis* in FAW control scenarios to maximize synergistic effects and achieve “1 + 1 > 2” control outcomes. This knowledge gap directly hinders the optimized integration and practical effectiveness of IPM strategies in the field.

Therefore, this study aims to address this critical knowledge gap by evaluating the compatibility of two mainstream commercial biopesticides in China—*B. thuringiensis* G033A and *M. anisopliae* CQMa421—with the egg parasitoid *T. chilonis*. Beyond direct toxicity tests, we focused on how pesticide application timing (pre- vs post-parasitism) affects key parasitoid performance metrics under laboratory and semi-field conditions. Specifically, we tested whether these microbial agents interfere with parasitoid fitness, can be safely co-deployed, or even exert synergistic effects in FAW control. The results will provide essential scientific support for developing IPM protocols combining microbial pesticides and natural enemies for sustainable FAW control.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Insects used for experiments

FAW egg masses used to start our colony for the indoor experiment were obtained from a maize field in Baozang Town, Jiangcheng County, Yunnan Province (22°41.23'N, 101°38.62'E). Once eggs hatched, the larvae were reared on maize leaves and artificial diet (Greene et al., 1976). Third instar larvae were removed from the mass rearing box and reared individually to avoid contamination. Pupae from individually reared older larvae were placed in a plastic box (25.5 × 12 × 10 cm) and held for adult emergence. Adults were held in insect-rearing cages (45 cm on a side) with 10 % honey water (Li et al., 2019a). FAW eggs on the walls of the cage were collected with a soft brush for 24 h and used for experiments. All rearing was done in an artificial climate chamber at 25 ± 1°C, 70 ± 5 % RH, and 14 L:10D photoperiod).

After microscopic examination with a stereomicroscope (SZ61, Olympus China Ltd., Beijing, China), 25 healthy, freshly laid FAW eggs (within 24 h post-oviposition) were fixed with white glue to a piece of paper (1.5 × 1.5 cm) to make egg cards to expose to parasitoids.

Corcyra cephalonica Stainton eggs that were parasitized by *T. chilonis* were obtained from Guangxi Nanning Heyi Biological Control Technology Co., Ltd. Nanning, China). For our indoor experiments were parasitized *C. cephalonica* eggs were held in glass tubes (2.5 cm dia × 10

cm), and adults of *T. chilonis* were collected as needed when they emerged.

2.2. Biopesticides

The two biopesticides used in the experiment were (1) *B. thuringiensis* G033A (*Bt*) Wettable powder (WP) supplied by Wuhan Kernel Bio-tech Co., Ltd. (Wuhan, China), with a toxicity titer of 32000 IU/mg; (2) *M. anisopliae* CQMa421 oil-based suspension concentrate (OD), provided by Chongqing Julixin Bioengineering Co., Ltd. (Chongqing, China), with a spore concentration of 8×10^9 spores/mL. A blank water control treatment was also run. The dosages of the biopesticides were determined according to the field recommendations: 3.375 kg/ha for *Bt* and 1.125 L/ha for *M. anisopliae*.

2.3. Direct toxic contact effects of two biopesticides on adults of *Trichogramma chilonis*

For our contact toxicity assay against adults of *T. chilonis*, we used the dry film residue technique of Desneux (Desneux et al., 2006). We pipetted 0.5 ml of the prepared insecticide solution (field rate, as described above) into a transparent glass tube (2.5 cm dia \times 10 cm). Then, the glass tube was continuously rolled on a self-rolling film preparation machine (adapted from an electric rolling machine, Guangdong Tang's Flower Industry and Trade Co., Ltd. Foshan, China) (Shen et al., 2024) until the solution uniformly covered the inner wall of the glass tube. Then the glass tube was placed in a cool, well-ventilated area and allowed to dry for 1.5 h at room temperature (approximately 25 °C). Subsequently, about 50 healthy adults of *T. chilonis* that had emerged within 12 h (Wang et al., 2005) were introduced, with cotton threads soaked in 10 % honey water provided as a food source. The mouths of the tubes were closed with a black cloth held in place with rubber bands, and then the tubes were placed in an artificial climatic chamber (25 \pm 1°C, 75 \pm 5 % RH, 14 L:10D). The parasitoids were exposed to the treated tube walls for 1 h before being removed (Ko et al., 2015). All exposed wasps were then moved into untreated clean glass tubes and provided with cotton threads soaked in 10 % honey water. These tubes were returned to the climatic chamber for 24 h. Tubes were then removed, and the number of surviving or dead parasitoids in each tube were counted. Parasitoids that did not move in response to tapping on the wall of glass tubes were considered dead. Abbott's formula was used to correct the mortality rate (Abbott, 1987). Each treatment had 25 replicate tubes.

2.4. Effect of pre-treatment of FAW eggs with biopesticides on subsequent parasitism rates

Two ml of a solution (label recommended rate) one of the biopesticides was pipetted into a Petri dish (3.5 cm dia), and then FAW egg cards were submerged in the solution for 30 s. For this bioassay, each card, prepared as described in section 2.1, bore 25 FAW eggs (within 24 h post-oviposition). Control cards were treated with 2 ml of water.

The cards were then air-dried at room temperature (approximately 25°C) for 1 h until both the egg masses and the card paper were completely dry, before being transferred into a glass tube (2.5 cm dia \times 10 cm). This process was repeated for all replicates of each of the two test materials (*Bt* and *M. anisopliae* spores) and the control.

Five healthy adult *T. chilonis* that had emerged within 12 h were introduced into each glass tube, consisting of 3 mated females and 2 males (to ensure that all females remained mated throughout the experiment) (Sattar et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2005). A cotton thread soaked in 10 % honey solution was also placed inside each tube. All female wasps had completed mating prior to the experiment, having been reared together with males from the laboratory population for 24 h post-emergence. Tubes were then placed in an artificial climatic chamber (at the same conditions as the rearing colony). The eggs were

observed daily. If FAW larvae emerged, they were removed, and the number of unparasitized eggs was recorded. After 2 days, the egg cards were observed under a stereomicroscope and the numbers of visibly parasitized (blackened) eggs parasitised were recorded. Eggs that did not turn black were considered unsuccessful, and the rate of parasitism was calculated for each replicate. Subsequently, the egg cards were placed in Petri dishes (6 cm dia) and observed every day for *T. chilonis* emergence. The number of parasitoids that emerged and the emergence dates were recorded. On the 14th day, the emergence holes on the FAW eggs were examined under a microscope, and the presence of round emergence holes on the darkened eggs was considered as the indication of successful emergence of *T. chilonis* adults. The successful emergence rate, the average number of wasps emerging per egg (some host eggs may yield more than one parasitoid upon emergence), and the average total number of emerged parasitoids were calculated for each treatment. Each treatment was replicated with 25 egg cards.

2.5. Effects of biopesticides applied to FAW eggs already parasitized by *T. Chilonis*

To obtain parasitized host eggs, FAW egg cards (each with 25 eggs within 24 h post-oviposition) were placed in glass tubes, together with 5 healthy adult wasps < 12 h old and cotton threads moistened with 10 % honey water. Tubes were then placed in an artificial climatic chamber at the same condition as for reared (see above). After 24 h of exposure, the adult wasps were removed from the test tube. Two days later, the FAW egg cards were examined, and the number of parasitized eggs (darkened) were counted. FAW egg cards were then immersed in a Petri dish (3.5 cm dia) containing one or the other of the two biopesticides being tested (solutions made to field-recommended dosage) or a water control for 30 s. Cards were then removed, allowed to dry for 1 h at room temperature (approximately 25 °C), and then transferred to a new Petri dish (6 cm dia). The subsequent checking for parasitoid emergence was the same as described above for pesticide exposure before parasitism (Tai et al., 2022).

2.6. Parameter calculation for pre- and post-exposure parasitism assays

The following parameters were calculated separately for each replicate of both the pre- and post-parasitism biopesticide application experiments:

(1) Pt (Parasitism rate for the biopesticide treatment) = Number of parasitized eggs in biopesticides treatment / Total number of eggs in biopesticides treatment; (2) Pc (Parasitism rate for the control treatment) = Number of parasitized eggs in control / Total number of eggs in control; (3) RP (Effect of biopesticides on parasitism rate) (%) = $(1 - Pt/Pc) \times 100$ (Hassan et al., 2000); (4) Et (Successful emergence rate under biopesticides treatment) = Number of successfully emerged eggs / Number of parasitized eggs; (5) Ec (Successful emergence rate of control) = Number of successfully emerged eggs / Number of parasitized eggs; (6) RE (Effect of biopesticides on successful emergence rate) (%) = $(1 - Et/Ec) \times 100$ (Manzoni et al., 2007); (7) Average number of wasps emerged per egg = Total number of emerged wasps / Number of parasitized host eggs from which parasitoids successfully emerged; (8) Average total number of emerged wasps = Total number of emerged wasps on day 14 / Number of repetitions.

2.7. Effect of two biopesticides in field trial on parasitism rate

In a maize field in Baozang Town, Jiangcheng County, Yunnan Province, one area was selected to evaluate the effect of releasing *T. chilonis* on FAW egg parasitism after the crop had been treated with one or the other of the two biopesticides or a water control. The biopesticides (*Bt* and *M. anisopliae*) were applied at the same recommended label rates as in the laboratory study, along with a control that was treated with water. The experiment was carried out inside 3 large field

cages (100 mesh, $5 \times 8 \times 2.5$ m, L, W, H), each of which was divided into three sections (i.e., plots). In the same cage, the same pesticide was sprayed, while the third cage served as the control and was treated with water. Materials were applied at the recommended field dosage using a 3WBD-20 L backpack hand-pressure sprayer (Shandong Zhongke Xinnong Aeronautical Technology Co., Ltd. Qingdao, China), at the equivalent rate of 300 L of solution of the formulated product per ha.

Parasitoids were introduced into the above field cages using egg cards, each card with about 1000 eggs. In each plot, we deployed 1 egg card by manually attaching them to the undersides of the leaves of the maize plants one day after pesticide application. A total of 3 egg cards were deployed across the 3 treatments (1 per cage \times 9 cages). Egg cards were deployed evenly throughout each plot, creating a release density of 7.5×10^5 parasitoids/ha (Dong et al., 2001; Muhammad et al., 2012).

To detect parasitism from the released wasps, we deployed 4 fresh FAW egg cards, one in each of the 3 plots in each cage. The deployment was conducted 4 days after the application of biopesticides, based on the predicted parasitoid emergence time, to ensure the wasps could locate and parasitize the eggs. The preparation of FAW egg cards (egg masses) was as follows: Eggs of FAW were collected from our laboratory-reared colony, and individual eggs were gently detached with a writing brush and then transferred onto egg cards, with 100 eggs per card (each egg card was defined as one egg mass in this study). All eggs on the cards were within 24 h of age when deployed to ensure uniform egg freshness.

The egg cards (egg masses) deployed to monitor parasitism inside cages were recovered 4 days after they were deployed without removing the natural egg masses in the field. Our FAW egg cards that were deployed to monitor the impact of the released parasitoids were marked with red tags. At the end of the 4-day deployment period, the monitoring egg cards were brought back to the laboratory and placed at room temperature. The parasitism rates were calculated in two dimensions: (1) Egg mass parasitism rate: the percentage of the 4 deployed egg cards (egg masses) per plot that were parasitized by *T. chilonis*; (2) Individual egg parasitism rate: for each parasitized egg card (egg mass), the percentage of individual eggs that were successfully parasitized. The rationale for evaluating both indices was to comprehensively reflect the parasitism efficiency of *T. chilonis*—egg mass parasitism rate reflects the host-locating ability of wasps at the aggregate egg level, while individual egg parasitism rate reflects the parasitizing ability of wasps within successfully located egg masses (Yuan et al., 2024).

2.8. Data analysis

Before conducting significance analysis, all percentage datasets were transformed to normalize the data, followed by normality verification using the Shapiro-Wilk test (Ghasemi and Zahediasl, 2012) and homogeneity of variance test via Levene's test. In our laboratory trial on adult parasitoid mortality following contact with pesticide residues in glass vials, we ran an analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's honest significant difference (HSD) test ($P < 0.05$) using SPSS 19.0 to identify differences in 24 h mortality (after exposure to biopesticides) among treatments.

In our laboratory trials on the effects of biopesticides applied on FAW eggs before they were exposed to parasitoid adults for parasitism ("pre-parasitism"), and a separate test on effects of biopesticides applied to FAW eggs after they had already been parasitized ("post parasitism"), we used one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's HSD test ($P < 0.05$) with SPSS 19.0 for mean comparison. The parameters analyzed in these two trials included: (1) parasitism rate, (2) parasitoid emergence rate, (3) number of wasps emerged per egg, (4) total number of emerged wasps per replicate, and (5) the parasitoid developmental duration. Additionally, t-tests were employed to analyze the effects of the same pesticide in the pre- and post-parasitism experiments following parameters: (1) successful emergence rate, (2) number of wasps emerged per egg, (3) average total number of emerged wasps, and (4) developmental duration.

For our field cage test, the parasitism rates for each treatment were compared with a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's HSD test ($P < 0.05$) with SPSS 19.0. Graphing for all results was done using GraphPad Prism 8 and Origin 2022.

Based on the classification system adopted by the International Organization for Biological Control (IOBC) (Sterk et al., 1999), the toxicity of biopesticides was categorized for discussion into four levels: 1: harmless (RE or RP $< 30\%$); 2: slightly harmful ($30\% < \text{RE or RP} < 79\%$); 3: moderately harmful ($80\% < \text{RE or RP} < 99\%$); 4: harmful (RE or RP $> 99\%$).

3. Results

3.1. Effects of two biopesticides on adult parasitoids in a residue contact assay

No significant difference was found for the direct toxicity of *Bt* ($10.7 \pm 1.6\%$), *M. anisopliae* ($10.4 \pm 1.9\%$), and the water control ($10.2 \pm 1.7\%$) after 24 h of exposure to residues of biopesticides applied at the recommended field dosages ($F = 0.051$, $df = 2$, $P > 0.05$). Following the criteria of the IOBC, both biopesticides were classified as harmless to adults of *T. chilonis*.

3.2. Effect on parasitism of applying biopesticides on host eggs before egg presentation to parasitoids ("pre-parasitism" assay)

In this assay, where biopesticides were applied to host eggs prior to exposing them to parasitoids, we observed no significant difference in parasitism rates between treatments: *Bt*-treated eggs ($80.9 \pm 3.6\%$), *M. anisopliae*-treated eggs ($74.0 \pm 3.9\%$), and water-treated control eggs ($84.1 \pm 2.9\%$) ($F = 2.385$, $df = 2$, $P > 0.05$). According to IOBC criteria, both biopesticides applied under these conditions would be classified as harmless to *T. chilonis*.

3.3. Effect of field cage applications of biopesticides on the parasitism of FAW egg cards

In field cage tests, when the two test biopesticides were applied to plants, we found no difference in parasitism of FAW egg cards placed in cages one day after pesticide applications, either on a per egg or per egg mass basis ($F = 0.528$, $df = 2$, $P > 0.05$) (Fig. 1).

3.4. Comparison of pesticide effects (pre-parasitism versus post-parasitism) on emergence of adult parasitoids

When *Bt* was applied within one day after *T. chilonis* parasitizes FAW eggs, although the successful emergence rate and the average number of wasps emerged per egg after parasitism and treatment show slight decreases compared to those when *Bt* is applied before parasitism, these differences were not significant ($P > 0.05$) (Table 1).

Regardless of whether different biopesticides were applied before or after *T. chilonis* parasitized FAW eggs, the average number of wasps emerged per egg ranged from 1.93 to 2.57. The number of wasps emerging per egg when biopesticides were applied post-parasitism was slightly lower than when applied pre-parasitism, but no significant differences were found ($P > 0.05$) (Table 1).

Comparing the impact of applying *Bt* applied pre- or post-parasitism on the number of wasps emerging per FAW eggs, we found that applying *Bt* post-parasitism significantly reduced the total number of emerged parasitoids ($t = 2.09$, $P = 0.04$) (Fig. 2).

3.5. Effect of application of biopesticides before or after egg parasitism on the developmental duration of *t. Chilonis*

Regardless of whether biopesticide treatments were applied before or after *T. chilonis* parasitized FAW eggs, the parasitoid emergence began

Fig. 1. Effect of biopesticides application inside field cages on parasitism rate of FAW egg cards placed in cages.

on the 5th day after parasitism and was largely completed by the 13th day (Fig. 3). There were no significant differences in the developmental duration (ranging from 7.55 to 8.79 d) between the treatments applied pre- and post-parasitism ($F = 1.316$, $df = 2$, $P > 0.05$; $F = 2.044$, $df = 2$, $P > 0.05$) (Fig. 4). Additionally, no significant differences were found between the biopesticides treatments and the control, indicating that these biopesticides, when applied pre- and post-parasitism of FAW eggs, had no negative impact on the developmental duration of *T. chilonis*.

Table 1

Effects of different biopesticides, applied before or after parasitism, on parasitoid emergence.

Treatment	Pre-parasitism	Avg. wasps/egg	Post-parasitism	Avg. wasps/egg	Sign. Pre vs post: SER (%)		Sign. Pre vs post: Avg. wasps/egg	
	SER (%)		SER (%)		T	P	T	P
Water	81.5 ± 3.9 aA	2.56 ± 0.21 aA	87.27 ± 2.95 aA	2.03 ± 0.18 aA	-0.86	0.40	1.96	0.28
<i>Bt</i>	70.3 ± 6.2 aA	2.32 ± 0.26 aA	65.47 ± 5.12 bA	2.14 ± 0.2 aA	1.36	0.19	0.54	0.59
<i>M. anisopliae</i>	78.8 ± 4.1 aA	1.95 ± 0.2 aA	82.12 ± 4.17 aA	1.93 ± 0.19 aA	-0.72	0.48	0.07	0.94

All data are means ± SE, lowercase letters indicate that there are significant differences in parameters among different treatment and the control pre or post parasitism, and uppercase letters indicate that there are significant differences in parameters between pre or post parasitism. (Duncan's, $P < 0.05$). Abbreviations: SER (%), Successful emergence rate (%); Avg. wasps/egg, Average number of wasps emerged per egg; Sign. Pre vs post: SER (%), Significance of difference in successful emergence of the same biopesticide applied pre- and post-parasitism; Sign. Pre vs post: Avg. wasps/egg, Significance of difference in average number of wasps emerged per egg for the same biopesticide applied pre- and post-parasitism.

Fig. 2. Effect of pre- vs. post-parasitism application of different biopesticides on the average total number of emerged wasps in *T. chilonis* under laboratory conditions. * Indicates a significant difference at $P < 0.05$ between two treatments. Pre = Pre-parasitism application; Post = Post-parasitism application.

4. Discussion

Tritrophic interactions were generally focused on arthropod natural enemies (Ali et al., 2023), insect pests and plants, while there is a big blank among the interactions of microbial agents, arthropod natural enemies and insect pests. This study assessed the safety of two biopesticides, *Bt* and *M. anisopliae*, to *T. chilonis*, a natural enemy of the FAW, by evaluating their direct contact toxicity and their effects on rates of parasitism, adult emergence, and developmental duration under both laboratory and field cage conditions. We found that, as per the categories of IOBC, both biopesticides were harmless to *T. chilonis* (IOBC Category 1: harmless, with the reduction rate of parasitoid performance $< 30\%$). However, *Bt* applications to eggs that were already parasitized did significantly reduce the successful emergence rate of adult parasitoids. Thus, during the period when *T. chilonis* is being released for FAW control, the use of either *Bt* or *M. anisopliae* to augment control is acceptable. However, if applying these biopesticides in combination with *T. chilonis* for FAW management in the field at or very near the same dates, *T. chilonis* should be released a day or so after pesticide application.

In the residual film test conducted in this study, the mortality rate of adult *T. chilonis* exposed to the recommended field doses of the two biopesticides for 24 h was approximately 10%. However, the direct contact toxicity of *Bt* to adults was slightly, but not significantly higher than that of *M. anisopliae*, which is consistent with previous reports (Amaro et al., 2015) for other *Trichogramma* species.

We integrated the results of our laboratory and field cage experiments to evaluate the impact of two biopesticides on the parasitic ability of *T. chilonis*. We found no significant difference in parasitism levels between treatments and the control, indicating that the two biopesticides, examined at the recommended field rate, do not significantly affect emergence of *T. chilonis* when applied on egg masses of FAW, either before or after parasitism. Similarly, in past studies the *Bt*

Fig. 3. Trends in daily average total number of *T. chilonis* under pre-parasitism conditions with biopesticides. (A) Trends in daily average total number of *T. chilonis* under post-parasitism conditions with biopesticides. (B).

Fig. 4. Effects of different biopesticides on the developmental duration of *T. chilonis* under laboratory conditions. Pre = Pre-parasitism application; Post = Post-parasitism application.

formulation Dipel WP, at low doses, has no significant impact on the parasitism efficiency of *T. chilonis* or *T. japonicum* Ashmead (Sharma and Aggarwal, 2019). Also, past studies have found minimal effects of treatment with either *M. anisopliae* or *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.-Criv.) Vuill. on the parasitism rates of *T. pretiosum* Riley or *Telenomus podisi* Ashmead (Pazini et al., 2016).

We did observe that application of *Bt* on parasitized host eggs did significantly reduce the rate of emergence of *T. chilonis*, with a reduction magnitude of approximately 23.5%. Notably, this reduction level remains below the harmless threshold (< 30%) defined by the IOBC classification system, indicating that *Bt* is still considered compatible with *T. chilonis* in integrated pest management (IPM) programs. This finding is of great importance for practical pest control recommendations: although *Bt* exhibits a slight adverse effect on parasitoid emergence, its overall safety profile allows it to be combined with *T. chilonis* releases for FAW control, provided that the temporal coordination between pesticide application and parasitoid release is optimized. Therefore, we recommend that growers avoid applying *Bt* shortly after making *T. chilonis* releases. In contrast, *M. anisopliae* applications were not subject to this limitation. Both findings are similar to past observations: Sharma and Aggarwal found that the *Bt* formulation Dipel WP had a relatively large impact on *Trichogramma* adult emergence, especially at dosage of 8.0 g/L and 6.0 g/L (Sharma and Aggarwal, 2019). Polanczyk et al. did not observe a negative impact of *M. anisopliae* (commercial strain E9) on the reproduction and survival of *T. atropovirilia* Oatman and Platner (Polanczyk et al., 2009), which is consistent with the findings of Antigo et al. for *T. galloi* Zucchi (Antigo et al., 2013).

In addition, entomopathogenic bacteria such as *Bt* must be ingested and enter midgut of insects to exert their virulence (Copping and Menn, 2000), while entomopathogenic fungi such as *M. anisopliae* can directly penetrate the insect cuticle via conidia to initiate infection (Ortiz-Urquiza and Keyhani, 2013). Based on this difference one might expect that the rate of successful adult parasitoid emergence from host eggs will be lower in the *M. anisopliae* treatment group. However, in our experiment, the adult parasitoid emergence rate in the *M. anisopliae* treatment group was 82.1%, compared to only 64.4% the *Bt* group. Peng et al. found that a silicone adjuvant added to the *M. anisopliae* formulation they used promoted conidial penetration of the host egg mass covering, increasing the infection rate of FAW eggs from 30% to over 90% (Peng et al., 2020). Simultaneously, in that study, they observed high infection rates of FAW eggs by *M. anisopliae*. However, we did not find such an effect for *M. anisopliae* with formulation used in our study. That more favorable outcome, combined with the lack of direct contact toxicity of *M. anisopliae* on *T. chilonis* adults (Perumal et al., 2024), suggested that *M. anisopliae* has high safety to *T. chilonis*, allowing parasitoid larvae to develop normally within exposed host eggs.

Neither of the two biopesticides in our study had any significant effects on the developmental duration of the immature stages of *T. chilonis*, either as a pre-parasitism application or as a post-parasitism application. Previous studies have shown that most biopesticides, such as *Bt* subsp. *kurstaki* (Vieira et al., 2001), do not significantly affect the development of *Trichogramma* species. However, some *Bt* formulations can delay prepupal development, prolong female longevity, or influence host-feeding behavior of *Trichogramma* species (Amichot et al., 2016;

Vieira et al., 2001). Also, the Unioeste 22 strain of *M. anisopliae* reduces the number of emerging parasitoids (Potrich et al., 2009). These differences may stem from factors such as inactive ingredients in formulations, strain-species virulence, physiological characteristics of parasitoids, or environmental conditions. Therefore, when using *Bt* or *M. anisopliae* together with parasitoid releases, such details must be considered.

Future research needs to consider the potential mechanisms of interaction between biopesticides and different parasitoid species, as well as how these interactions are modulated by environmental conditions, to accurately assess potential risks and benefits of integrating biopesticides with augmentative biological control releases. Our study offers support for the integrated management of FAW using either *Bt* or *M. anisopliae* in conjunction with *T. chilonis*. Understanding the impacts of biopesticides on parasitoids should allow risks to be mitigated in many cases. For example, the release strategy and its timing might need to be adjusted based on the potential effects of biopesticides on parasitoids as we suggest in this study, relatively to not applying *Bt* and *T. chilonis* on the same day. Such coordination based on research will enhance the efficiency and sustainability of biological control strategies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yuanyuan Cheng: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Hongmei Li:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Xianming Yang:** Investigation. **Suqin Shang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Abdul Aziz Bukero:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Feng Zhang:** Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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